

The Application of Solochrome Fast Navy 2 RS as an Indicator for Complexometric Titrations

P. N. GUPTA, C. N. KACHRU and (Miss) SHAMIM A. BHAT

Department of Chemistry, The University of Kashmir, Sringar-190 006, India

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Solochrome Fast Navy 2 RS, a water soluble azo dye, is found to be a very useful complexometric indicator for Ca(II), Mg(II), admixture of Ca(II) -Mg(II), Zn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), Ni(II), Pb(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) titrations with EDTA.

THE use of Eriochrome Black T as a complexometric indicator is well known¹, but this has some drawbacks in some cases. Solochrome Fast Navy 2 RS which closely resembles Eriochrome Black T has shown more promising results as a complexometric indicator.

Experimental

Apparatus : The titrations were performed at room temperature (20°) with standard Corning (India) volumetric ware and for titrations at higher temperature, a thermostat (Tempo, India) with an accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$ was used. A pH meter model 820, (Trombay Electronic Instruments, India) was employed for adjusting the pH.

Reagents :

(a) **Dyes :** Solochrome Fast Navy 2 RS (I.C.I., India), is soluble in water and after repeated recrystallization gives a violet coloured solid having an absorption maximum at 530 nm. The purified dye gives a single spot on chromatographic paper (Whatmann No 1) bearing R_f value of ca.0.65 with the solvent 1.5 N NH₄OH saturated with n-butanol. 0.5g of dye was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and was stored in tightly closed bottle. The solution so prepared retains *indicator* its properties even after one year of its continuous use.

Eriochrome Black T (E. Merck) solution was prepared by the method recommended by Brown and Hayes².

(b) All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The appropriate salts of the metal ions Mg(II), Ca(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Ni(II), Pb(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) were prepared in distilled water.

(c) **EDTA :** A standard EDTA solution was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of disodium salt in distilled water.

(d) **Buffers :** NH₄OH-NH₄Cl buffer³ of pH 10, NH₄OH-NH₄Cl buffer of pH 8.5 sodium tartrate-

NaOH buffer of pH 9.5 and H₃PO₄, CH₃COOH, H₃BO₃-NaOH buffer⁴ of pH 2.4 were prepared by standard methods.

Results and Discussion

Solochrome Fast Navy 2 RS possesses acid-base indicator properties and therefore requires the maintenance of close control of pH using buffer solutions. The two phenolic groups provide two dissociable protons with pK values 6.4 and 11.6. The colour variations are red below pH 5.5, blue violet between pH 7.0 and 12.0 and blood red above pH 13.0. The possible structures associated with the change in pH are shown in the next page.

The optimum experimental conditions for different metal ions using this indicator are summarised in Table 1. The complexometric titrations performed with this indicator show that the results are within experimental errors. Copper(II) could be titrated at 80-85° after reduction to Cu(I) with Na₂SO₃. Salts of lead and iron could be titrated using sodium tartrate-sodium hydroxide and Britton-Robinson buffers respectively to avoid their precipitation in ammoniacal medium. Salts of calcium, magnesium and their admixture could successfully be titrated by this indicator with a procedure similar to that using Eriochrome Black T, with the added advantage that the colour changes are much sharper. Similar is the case with Zinc, Cadmium and Nickel. The direct titration of cobalt by this method is not feasible due to the formation of a more stable complex of dye with Co(II)⁵. Sharp end point could however, be obtained by performing back titration in the presence of excess of EDTA using ZnSO₄ as titrant.

In many cases Solochrome Fast Navy 2 RS gives comparable results while with some metal ions e.g. Pb(II) and Cu(II) it is better than other related two dyes (i.e. Eriochrome Black T and Solochrome Blue Black B). In the case of Fe(III) and Ni(II) it can be used for direct titration. Another advantage is the ease of the preparation of its solution and its higher stability in pure aqueous medium as compared to Eriochrome Black T⁶.

TABLE 1—COMPLEXOMETRIC TITRATION OF METAL IONS WITH STANDARD EDTA USING SOLOCHROME FAST NAVY 2 RS AS INDICATOR (0.2 ml of 0.5% AQUEOUS SOLUTION).

S. No.	Metal	Buffer	pH	Temperature °C	Color transition at the end point
1.	Mg(II)	NH ₄ OH-NH ₄ Cl	10.0	20	Rose red to violet
2.	Ca(II)	NH ₄ OH-NH ₄ Cl	10.0	20	Rose red to violet
3.	Ca(II), Mg(II)	NH ₄ OH-NH ₄ Cl	10.05	20	Pink to violet
4.	Zn(II)	NH ₄ OH-NH ₄ Cl	9.95	20	Pink to violet
5.	Cu(II) titrated as Cu(I)	NH ₄ OH-(Conc.)	12.15	80-85	Red to blue
6.	Cd(II)	NH ₄ OH-NH ₄ Cl	10.00	20	Rose red to violet
7.	Ni(II)	NH ₄ OH-NH ₄ Cl	8.55	45-60	Wine red to deep blue
8.	Pb(II)	Sod. Tartrate-NaOH	9.50	50	Violet to red
9.	Fe(III)	Britton-Robinson*	2.40	40-50	Brown to orange

*H₃PO₄, CH₃COOH, H₃BO₃, -NaOH buffer

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